

BB 2208

Human Resource Management

Name: Mohammad Alim Bin Haji Edin

Reg Id: 19B1091

School: School of Business and Economics

Tutorial: Wednesday@9.50am

Assignments Title:

Company: Syarikat Al Rasyid

Contents

1. Introduction	4
2. Challenges or problems in Syarikat Al-Rasyid	6
3. Case analysis: Solution to the challenges using Fombrun model and alternate solution.....	7
4. Advantages of disadvantages of implementing Fombrun model in Company Al-Rasyid.....	8
5. Conclusion.....	9

Executive Summary

This report introduces the Youth Potential Agripreneurs in Brunei and the company who is considered as the pioneers in the Brunei Agriculture industry. The vision of this report is to initiate the meaning of Human Resource management mode and how it can help create momentum in the business effectiveness and the advantages and disadvantages of implementing the model. I will also be addressing the issues and problem that surface during the operation of the company and how the model can solve the problem.

1. Introduction

The world is now evolving into more technological and theory approach. In order to keep up with the trend, Business need to adapt well and do their research on what approach they should implement on their business. Business who don't adapt well to the society trend will find it hard to make a breakout in the industry and market targeted. It is because they are way behind their competitors who has implemented the system well in their company.

In Brunei Darussalam., Technology and theorist approach are not in par with other developing countries. We are way behind in term of the technologies but its currently booming with everything has been adapted to digital and theoretical based on the Syariah Law. Now, Brunei Darussalam has been dependent on oil and gas industry sector. Where most of Brunei Gross Domestic Product (GDP) came from it. Since oil and gas are not unlimited resource, Brunei has now turned its attention to other sectors, such as Agriculture and Tourism sector. Both Agriculture and Tourism Brunei has been booming, its all thanks to Brunei implementing the Syariah Law which has gain attention from people around the world.

There are many notable companies in Brunei Darussalam who has been making name in the Agriculture industry, such as Ideal Multifeed farm who owned farm and restaurant chains in Brunei and Soto Rindu restaurant and Catering/Katimahar Agri Park that has been known as one of local company who has variety of business in different sectors including the Agriculture industry. In this report, I will be introducing you a company who has potential to be one of the headliners in the Agriculture industry in the future.

1.1 Introduction to Syarikat Al – Rasyid

Syarikat Al-Rasyid was founded on 4th October 2015 by Muhammad Abdul Rasyid bin Kamarudjaman. The business is specialized in agriculture industry that focused on its paddy cultivation. The paddy farm is managed on 1 hectare of land in Kampong Bebuloh. He makes his first step by joining a course in Belia Berpadi course in January 2015. The reason he participated in this course is because he doesn't have any background or prior experience in Paddy cultivation. (Musa, Idris & Basir, 2020) He became a certified paddy cultivator in 16th July 2015 after complete his Belia Berpadi Course. This is when he received his 1-hectare plot of Land to start his business. After completing his licensed Rasyid the founder started his theory and practice lessons by Paddy Unit of the Department of Agriculture (DAA) and also, he was enrolled in classes provided by Rice Farmers Field School (RFFS). This course has made Rasyid business go one step further in the paddy cultivation. He learns everything he needs from land cultivations and selection to nutrient and water management. Two years later he was chosen to participate in a training course for "Hybrid Rice Comprehensive Technology for Developing Countries" which was fully funded by The China ministry of Commerce (Musa, Idris & Basir, 2020). In my opinion, Rasyid greatest traits is that his greed for knowledge, after completing his courses in China. He sought out for mentors to gain more knowledge. These mentors are all well-known paddy cultivator that mostly are part of the Majlis Perundingan Kampong Limau Manis.

1.2 Introduction to Human Resource Model.

In the early 1980s, there are many Human resource management model that was introduced by theorist. It aims to manage employee on many criterias such as the Employee satisfaction, recruitment selection and retention. Fombrun model was the first Human management model to be introduced, followed by Harvard model by Michael Beer in 1984, The guest model by David Guest in 1989, The Warwick model by Chris Hendry in the early 1900s and many more. But in this report, I will be focusing on the very first Human Resource Management model which is The Fombrun model.

Fombrun Model is the very first Human Resource Management that was introduced in the early 1984. It works closely to the Organisation strategy. It functions on 4 aspects to make sure the organisation work fully on its effectiveness. The 4 aspect are selection, , appraisals, development, reward and their interrelatedness. This model was emphasizing more on the tight fit between Human Resource strategy and Business overall strategy and goal. Its purpose is to matched the available human resource to jobs in the organisation. To ensure that the human resource strategy is in correlation with the business strategy, the organisation need to keep track with their Human resource efficiently hence this model is the perfect fit for it. In this model, it fully utilized every other resource so the goals of the organisation can be achieved. The other benefits of this model are that it can help business to achieve physical labor at lower cost with other great benefits to employee such as appraisal and rewards. ill be explaining all aspect of the Fombrun model:

The Fombrun Model of HRM (1984)

Figure 1 Fombrun model. cr. Professional Shiksha

- Recruitment selection:
Its purpose is to recruit the right people for the right job in the organisation, to make sure they the employee that are hired know what they are doing in the company. it depends on how they implement the recruitment selection system. Some organisation do it formally and vice versa.
- Reward
Giving reward to the employee in the company is must in today society to make them satisfied with the workplace. Usually the reward given are based on the workers worth of work. In today society organisation are implementing bonus salary system. For example, a special trip given or discounted ticket price to employee in the airlines industry.
- Appraisal
Appraisal in company will be differ and will need to be changed based on the society trend. It measures individual performance. It aims to make sure the employee is on the right track. It can also be used to keep track return on investment.
- Development
Development and training in organisation are vital in every organisation. Employee in organisation need to evolve in terms of skills so they can gain competitive advantage against the competitors. Development and training can also be done informally by having mentor's system.

2. Challenges or problems in Syarikat Al-Rasyid

Land Fertility

Since the early stage of the business, Rasyid has overcome many problems. Some of the problem can be solved systemically and theoretically using the HRM model such as Fombrun model. At the beginning stage, the land he received from "Kursus Belia Berpadi" community is not in good condition and is inconsistent in terms of fertility. Rasyid also need to do the labor work manually since the land are really damn and small for machines or working animal to go into. Because of this, Rasyid need to toil the land for long hours to make sure the land is fertile and in good condition to farm in the long run since its they only farm This has greatly affected the business productivity level and the reason why the product quality is modest.

Lack of infrastructure

Managing the farm without proper infrastructure such as water and machines will affect the business productivity. Rasyid also complain with the poorly constructed road in his farm areas. Which make it hard to access the farm. There is some infrastructure provided in Wasan but it was for sharing purposes between the farmers accordingly to their specific schedule. And Rasyid said also his business and other farmers are also dependent on rainy weather to water their farms.

Financial Problem

The government only give Rasyid a physical asset which is land. Rasyid has received financial support from the livewire organisation to kickstart his business. He also received financial backup from his family. But to start and to beneficially exploit the agriculture industry market. The capital is not sufficient to run the business. To run the business in long term, he need loan from bank, friend or look for investors.

Labour

In the farm ,he doesn't have many workers helping him. He was only helped by his family and friends to do his farm works. It's very hard to get employees, that's because working in farm is very hard under the scorching heat and working outdoor and farming require a great patience and resilience.

3. Case analysis: Solution to the challenges using Fombrun model and alternate solution

To solve the problem related to its financially problem, Rasyid should find an investor who is willing to invest in his business so he can compete with other company in the same industry. Finding a investor will be easy for Rasyid company since he has achieved a lot under his names such as "Usahawan Belia Aktif award" and many more. He also has attended many courses which can reduce the investor risk and put his trust more into Rasyid company. And also, Rasyid should try getting investment from The Darussalam Dare Enterprise. Dare has helped man Smes in Brunei, they will be willing since Brunei economic has turn its attention to the agriculture industry. So, it will be a win-win situation with Brunei economy and Rasyid company.

After acquiring the investment, Rasyid should hire an agriculture land specialist to measure and overcome any difficulties or Risk in his farm. Hiring a permanent land specialist to work in his farm will be beneficial for Al – Rasyid company, it will increase their productivity output level.

Regarding the lack of infrastructure such as bad condition of road in the farm which leading to many negative factors to the business. this is going to be hard since repairing a road required a permission and should be requested to the governments, without their permission Al-Rasyid can't do anything.

In the meanwhile, Rasyid should hire more workers or farmers to work under him and delegates his work to his workers so he can focus on the internal and external strategy planning of his company. Since hiring workers is costly but hiring need to be done

By implementing the Fombrun model in Al-Rasyid company, he can start managing employee from the beginning in recruitment selection. He needs to hire people who has the patience to work outdoor under the scorching heat and knowledge or any prior experience in cultivating paddy. This will be beneficial for the Al-Rasyid company since it's the company will take less time to make sure he is ready to be working on the field.

Then after careful selection on the employee recruitment, working outside in the farm can be stressful and demotivated for the employee leading them to leave the company. Fombrun model appraisal and reward system can be put into good use. Al-Rasyid should implement a bonus reward system in the company. it will motivate the employee to work and also attract more people to work in the company which is beneficial. After careful appraisal on the individual, the company should reward them on their work. There should be a system that will make employee more motivated to work such as Employee of the month or year reward.

The aim of Fombrun model is to make the core of the business is stable so the business can operate fully on its effectiveness. So, development and training are key to organisation effectiveness. Al-Rasyid should provide training courses to its employee for the benefits of the company and individuals. Another alternative solution to higher cost of training courses is informal training which is mentor system. Al-Rasyid should apply this system since its not costly and in my opinion, mentorship system is better than any other development training.

4. Advantages of disadvantages of implementing Fombrun model in Company Al-Rasyid

Implementing Fombrun model of Human resource can be a positive and negative news to the Al-Rasyid company. Since it is the first ever model to be introduce, so there are many aspects need to be improved on. To begin with, the Fombrun only focus on 4 factors which is recruitment Selection, Appraisal, Rewards and Development, The Fombrun model ignore other factors that can influence the business. the advantages and disadvantages of the Fombrun model are as follows:

Advantages

- Market performance and organizational growth

Implementing this model will allow managers or owners to manage and keep track with its resource at finest. With careful handling of resource will also be beneficial for the employee to keep track with the market. Hence it will improve the internal and external growth of the business. If Al-Rasyid company apply this model to its business core, the organisation will grow more fully to its fullest potential so it can compete with the Brunei pioneers in the Agriculture industry.

Disadvantages

- Market failure due to ignorance of the environment

Fombrun model is incomplete as it only focusses on the four factors, it fails to recognized environmental factors. This could be a problem to Al-Rasyid company since environmental factors are the key in agriculture industry such as scarcity of resource like food and water, weather that could damage the paddy cultivation.

5. Conclusion

So, adapting to the current society trend is really important for any business and organizations. In this modern day, the trends are contingent and evolving faster, business need to adapt really well in order to compete in the industry. So, in this case, Al – Rasyid company should really consider on implementing Fombrun model to its business.

6. Reference

Anthony S K, (2018), Soft and Hard HRM, Retrieved from: <https://www.slideshare.net/AnthonySadallaKhamis/soft-and-hard-hrm-presentation>

Exam night live, (2020), HRM MODELS, Retrieved from: <https://examnightlive.wordpress.com/2016/04/24/hrm-models/>

HR Knowledge, (2015), Model of Human Resource Management, Retrieved from: <http://nehaspeakshr.blogspot.com/2015/07/models-of-human-resource-management.html>

Jagwan S, (2015), Model of Human Resource Management, Retrieved from: <http://professionalshiksha.blogspot.com/2015/10/models-of-human-resource-management.html>

Musa, S, D, P, D, H., Pg Hj Idris, P. S. R., & Basir, K.H (2020), Inspiring Agripreneurs of Brunei, Unissa Press, Universiti Islam Sultan Sharif Ali

Vishal T, Shivani S & Pankaj K, (2019), *Adaptation of HRM Practices: A practice model – case study of a hotel*, PP 59-63 8. Volume 21, Issue 4. Ser. I, Retrieved from: <http://www.iosrjournals.org/>